

K-MoCo: a k-space rigid motion correction approach for first-pass perfusion cardiac MR

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Summary: Motion correction (MoCo) in free-breathing first-pass perfusion CMR (pCMR) is usually resolved in image space, requiring an initial reconstruction. We propose an inter-frame pairwise rigid MoCo approach formulated exclusively in k-space. Preliminary results show its potential for respiratory MoCo in pCMR.

Introduction: First-pass perfusion cardiac MR (pCMR) enables the non-invasive diagnosis of ischemic heart disease by capturing a sequence of images during the rapid passage of a contrast bolus through the heart [1]. Traditionally, patients were instructed to hold their breath to reduce image blurring and misalignments caused by respiratory motion. However, there is a growing preference to acquire images during free-breathing (FB) due to increased reliability and patient comfort [1]. Consequently, the integration of inter-frame motion correction (MoCo) methods to align the sequence of images is crucial for both FB acquisitions and correcting any remaining motion artifacts stemming from inadequate breath-holding.

Typically, MoCo methods in pCMR are formulated as registration problems in the image domain [2-4] using multimodal similarity metrics to deal with the dynamic contrast. Alternatively, motion could be estimated and corrected directly from k-space data avoiding the need for initial image reconstruction. In this work, we propose K-MoCo, an inter-frame rigid MoCo approach for pCMR that performs exclusively on k-space data.

Methods:

Digital phantom: The MRXCAT numerical phantom [5] was used to generate fully-sampled pCMR data with the following parameters: FOV = 320 × 320 mm², in-plane resolution = 1.6×1.6 mm², slice thickness = 5 mm, 1 slice, 32 time frames, $TS/TR/TE=150.0/2.0/1.0$ ms, flip angle = 15°, contrast agent dose = 0.075 mmol/kg, and contrast agent relaxivity = 5.6 L/mmol s. Next, after an image intensity normalization the k-space was constructed for the whole sequence.

Theory:

The proposed rigid k-space MoCo approach performs pairwise to align each frame to a common reference. To avoid the variations in module and phase caused by dynamic contrasts, the normalized cross correlation (NCC) was employed as the optimization metric but defined between the corrected k-space (S_c) and the reference k-space (S_f).

Thus, the optimization problem consists in finding the parameters $\Theta = \begin{bmatrix} \Theta_R \\ \Theta_T \end{bmatrix}$, with $\Theta_R = [\theta_1 \cdots \theta_n]^T$ and $\Theta_T = [u_1 \ u_2 \ u_3]^T = [\theta_{n+1} \ \theta_{n+2} \ \theta_{n+3}]^T$, where subscripts R and T stand for rotation and translation, that minimize the following cost function:

$$V(\Theta) = -|NCC(S_f, S_c(\Theta))|^2$$

Its derivatives are given by:

$$\frac{\partial V_{\Theta}}{\partial \theta_p} = -2\Re \left\{ \frac{\partial NCC(\Theta)}{\partial \theta_p} NCC^* \right\},$$

where

$$NCC(S_f, S_c(\Theta)) = \frac{N(\Theta)}{D(\Theta)} = \frac{\sum_{\mathbf{k}} S_f(\mathbf{k}) S_c^*(\mathbf{k}; \Theta)}{\sqrt{\underbrace{\sum_{\mathbf{k}} |S_f(\mathbf{k})|^2}_E \underbrace{\sum_{\mathbf{k}} |S_c(\mathbf{k}; \Theta)|^2}_F}}$$

where

$$S_c(\mathbf{k}; \Theta) = S_m(\mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{k}) e^{j2\pi \Theta^T \mathbf{k}}$$

is the k-space corrected with the estimated rigid transformation, since rotation and translation of the object in image space correspond to a rotation and a linear phase-shift in k-space. $S_m(\mathbf{k})$ models the rotation-corrupted k-space and \mathbf{R} is a rotation matrix. To avoid interpolation errors in k-space, which lead to blurring of the image, the rotation is implemented following the 3-shears methodology defined in [6]. The optimization problem was solved by means of a nonlinear conjugate gradient algorithm with backtracking line search [7].

Experiments:

Random translations (u_1 and u_2 between -10 and 10 voxels) and rotations (θ_1 between 0° and 15°) are independently simulated in k-space of each frame. Frame 24 was empirically selected as reference, thereby no degradation was included. s three different initialization values were applied. Ultimately, the selected estimate was the one that achieved the lowest NCC value.

Results:

Figure 1 shows, for the whole pCMR sequence, the images reconstructed from both the motion-corrupted and the motion-corrected k-spaces. Temporal intensity profiles in x-t and y-t directions are shown in Figure 2. Finally, the scatter plots of the ground-truth and estimated parameters for rotations and translations are shown in Figure 3. The mean squared error (MSE) values were $1.46e^{-4}$, $12.06e^{-4}$, and $23.65e^{-4}$ for θ_1 , u_1 , and u_2 , respectively. The total time for motion estimation and correction in k-space was 107.62 s for the whole sequence.

Discussion & Conclusions: We proposed K-MoCo, an inter-frame pairwise rigid MoCo approach formulated exclusively in the k-space domain. The proposed approach was validated with a digital phantom. As can be seen in the results, the formulation we proposed was able to estimate the rigid registration parameters (i.e., θ_1 for rotation, and u_1 , and u_2 for translation) with high accuracy (MSE < $5e^{-3}$ for the three of them). Thus, preliminary results on synthetic phantom data show the potential for conducting respiratory MoCo in pCMR directly in k-space. Notice that respiration motion implies, to a large extent, a rigid transformation of the heart region, although elastic deformations may also arise. Future work includes the validation of the proposed approach with real prospectively undersampled data.

References:

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Figure 1: Comparison between the motion-corrupted and the motion-corrected sequences for the digital phantom data. a) Motion-corrupted sequence with a rigid deformation, b) motion-corrected sequence after applied the estimated parameters, and c) overlay between both. The sequences are shown in a region of interest (ROI) defined to include the heart.

Figure 2: Temporal intensity profiles for a) the motion-corrupted and b) the motion-corrected sequences in the directions of x-t (horizontal orange line, first row) and y-t (vertical green line, second row).

Figure 3: Scatter plots of the estimated versus ground-truth registration parameters values for θ_1 (rotation), and u_1 and u_2 (translation of the scanned object). Note that the number of points corresponds to the number of frames. The diagonal line represents the identity.